

Hierarchical Symbolic Pop Music Generation with Graph Neural Networks

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Abstract. Music is inherently made up of complex structures, and representing them as graphs helps to capture multiple levels of relationships. While music generation has been explored using various deep generation techniques, research on graph-related music generation is sparse. Earlier graph-based music generation worked only on generating melodies, and recent works to generate polyphonic music do not account for longer-term structure. In this paper, we explore a multi-graph approach to represent both the rhythmic patterns and phrase structure of Chinese pop music. Consequently, we propose a two-step approach that aims to generate polyphonic music with coherent rhythm and long-term structure. We train two Variational Auto-Encoder networks: one on a MIDI dataset to generate 4-bar phrases, and another on song structure labels to generate full song structure. Our work shows that the models are able to learn most of the structural nuances in the training dataset, including chord and pitch frequency distributions, and phrase attributes.

Keywords: Music generation · Graph neural network · Symbolic music generation.

1 Introduction

Music, an intricate tapestry of rhythm, melody, and harmony, is inherently structured in a way that lends itself well to graph representations. At a higher level, music can be viewed as a progression of sections and phrases, while at a more granular level, it is made up of complex interplay of notes, chords, and rhythms. Both levels of music structure can intuitively be captured in graphs. Meanwhile, symbolic music formats (e.g. MIDI, XML) contain structured information about pitch, duration, onset time, and tracks [2]. This makes symbolic music an ideal format to be represented as graphs [28, 17].

Music generation has seen rapid advancements, particularly with the increasing popularity of text-to-audio models [3, 19, 18] that create complete songs from text

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prompts. While raw audio generation has the advantage of producing high-fidelity music that can be used for creative purposes, it lacks the level of customization needed for music composition and arrangement. Symbolic music allows for more precise control over musical elements like melody, harmony, and rhythm.

Symbolic music generation has made great progress in capturing inter-track relationships like chords and rhythm [14], but still struggle with long term structure. [25, 20] While work like MELONS [29] and PopMNet [24] have found success in generating longer forms of music using graph representations, they work only on melodies instead of polyphonic music. Conversely, work like Polyphemus [4] have successfully generated structured polyphonic music using graph representations, but barely extends beyond a few bars. An intuitive question arises: can we derive a model that creates both polyphonic and long-term music?

In this paper, we aim to generate polyphonic symbolic music with long-term structure with a hierarchical two-stage framework. First, we train two separate Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE)s to encode and decode graph representations of song and phrase structures respectively. Each VAE encodes its input as an embedding in a latent space. Using the trained VAEs, we then generate new song structure and phrases by passing a random latent embedding through the model's decoder. Combining the two models, the generated phrases are interpolated according to the song structure to form coherent phrases that make up a song.

The contributions of the paper are:

1. We proposed a novel graph representation that captures song structure based on POP909 structural annotation, including the relationships between phrases, and the phrase attributes.
2. We explored the use of VAE graph network for song structure generation based on the proposed structure graph. We then employed a two-stage approach that combines 4-bar phrase prediction and structure prediction.
3. We conducted in-depth evaluation analysis regarding the structural aspect that follows existing literature, demonstrating that our generated songs have structure that is closer to human-composed songs.

2 Related Work

The problem we have laid out concerns three areas of research: (A) Symbolic music generation, (B) Graph representations of music, and (C) Graph generation. Each will be discussed in their respective sections below.

2.1 Symbolic Music Generation

One of the challenges in symbolic music generation lies in capturing the intricacies and multi-faceted qualities [20, 26, 27] of human-composed music. Bhandari et al. [1] compared different structure representations of symbolic music, and found that music generation still faces the challenges of “modelling nuanced development and variation of themes much like human compositions across extended periods”.

Dai et al. [6, 8] found that generated music lacked structural properties that were in human-created music. These include phrase structure, chord and melody progressions, in which generated music failed to capture the varying patterns of entropy at different parts of the song. In a separate study [7], Dai analyzed the relationship between the structure of music and the elements of harmony, melody, and rhythm, and found that patterns in harmony and melody were related to hierarchical structure. Dai’s analysis metrics in both studies informs the evaluation methods in our paper.

Prior work [11, 22] have attempted generating longer sequences of music with limited success. Mittal et al. [21] explored diffusion architecture to generate long-term melodies, and Zou et al. [29] explored a graphRNN approach.

2.2 Graph Representation of Music

One of the core advantage of graph representation of music is the flexibility of design, which can be customized based on the needs of individual music information retrieval (MIR) tasks. The most common one is to construct note-level nodes and construct edges based on note relationships [13, 17, 28]. There are also works on bar-level [4] and even phrase-level [29] node designs.

Research exploring graph representations of music have shown the potential for graph models to perform well in tasks that benefit from learning structural information, such as music classification [9, 28], modelling perceptual musical similarity [23], and modelling expressive music performances [13]. Furthermore, they provide explainability, and quantify relative importance of various features of the note [16].

2.3 Music Graph Generation

While there have been research [15, 10] on graph representations of music for various music tasks, few have explored using graphs for music generation. In particular, two key studies, PopMNet [24], and MELONS [29] have been pivotal to the study of music generation using graph neural networks (GNNs).

PopMNet introduced a pioneering approach by utilizing a chord-progression and melody structure graph to generate pop music melodies [24]. It successfully captured musical dependencies, but was limited to single-track melodies only. MELONS built on PopMNet by incorporating a bar-level relationship graph and using GraphRNN with Transformer models to capture long-term structure in melodies [29]. This enabled the generation of coherent melodies over extended periods, but is still lacks inter-track information such as chords and accompaniment. Additionally, the evaluation relied heavily on subjective methods, and lacks quantitative measures of its generative ability.

Cosenza et al. [4] introduced Polyphemus, a GraphVAE based model capable of generating polyphonic, multi-instrument music using a chord-level graph. The model generated music that was coherent in rhythm and pitch across multiple tracks, which was an improvement over melody-only models like PopMNet and

MELONS. The model was highly reproducible, with clear evaluation of the latent space. However, Polyphemus still lacked long-term structure.

Although these studies show the potential for graph-based music generation, challenges such as long-term structure and multi-instrumentality have great room for exploration.

Fig. 1. Two-step hierarchical approach: Music is made up of phrases, and each phrase can be sectioned into bars. We train a model for each level of hierarchy.

3 Methodology

We propose GraphMuGen, a two-step approach that uses two generative models, a *phrase generation model*, and a *song structure generation model*, to generate polyphonic music with coherent long-term structure, as illustrated in Figure 1.

3.1 Dataset and preprocessing

To generate Chinese pop music, we used POP909 for training both the phrase generation and structure generation models. POP909 consists of 909 Chinese Pop songs in MIDI format, with 3 tracks per song: Melody, Bridge, and Piano accompaniment. We also use structure labels of POP909 [7], which are human-labelled, and contains information about the phrase types (i.e. intro, melodic, non-melodic, bridge, outro), and the phrase length in number of bars.

For phrase generation, we filtered the data for 4/4 time songs only. Each song is then split into phrases based on the structure labels. Phrases that are longer than 4-bars are split further to ensure that all phrases are 4-bars long (e.g. 7 bars are split into 4-bars, and (3 + 1 empty bar) tracks). Those with two concurrent empty bars are dropped.

This method of pre-processing differs from Polyphemus, which extracted a moving window of N-bars. While a moving window creates a larger and more

varied dataset, it loses the structural information within each phrase, since each example could contain bars in between phrases. Hence, we split them by phrases to ensure that the model learns structure within a phrase. Arguably, some structural information is still lost when we split 8-bar phrases into 2×4 -bar phrases.

For structure generation, the phrase labels were processed to extract the encoded phrase type and phrase lengths. Songs with more than 12 phrases were truncated (i.e. only the first 12 are included). For both models, we used a train-val-test split of 70-20-10.

3.2 Graph Representation

Fig. 2. Graph representation of phrase structure of a single bar (left) and song structure (right) in POP909.

Bar Level At the bar level, we adopt Polyphemus’ method of graph representation (Figure 2). Each node in the graph represents a chord at a single time step in each track. A chord is defined as a group of notes played concurrently in a single track. Connecting the nodes are three types of edges, representing different relationships between the nodes: (i) Next Edges connect consecutive nodes across different tracks, (ii) Track edges connect consecutive nodes within the same track, and (iii) Onset edges connect nodes with the same onset time, across all tracks. Each node is represented by an encoding of its Content, which contains information about the pitch and duration of each pitch.

Phrase Level For song structure generation, the graph is at phrase-level. Each node represents a 4-bar phrase (Figure 2). There are two types of graph edges: (i) Next edges, which connect consecutive phrases, and (ii) Melody/Non-Melody edges, which connect consecutive melody/non-melody phrases. Similar to the Bar-level nodes, each Phrase-level node is represented by an encoding of its Content, which contains information about the phrase length (i.e. number of bars), and phrase type (e.g.. intro/outro, bridge, etc.).

3.3 Model Architecture

Both the *phrase generation* and *song structure generation* models use a similar architecture inspired by the Polyphemus model, as shown in Figure 3. Each model is a VAE which contains two key components: a structure encoder/decoder, and a content encoder/decoder.

Fig. 3. Model VAE Architecture. Both models follow a similar architecture.

Polyphemus Architecture The content encoder uses a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN), and is responsible for encoding information about pitch and duration, while taking into account the structure of the bars. It works by first encoding the pitch and duration of notes into note embeddings (N), and then encoding N into a chord representation. The chord representation is then passed through the GCN with the bar-level graph representation. The GCN outputs an embedding for each chord, which is compressed into a bar-level content embeddings. They are then concatenated and further compressed to obtain a content embedding (Zc).

The structure encoder is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with two convolutional layers that takes in a structure tensor representing node activations across time for each track (i.e. whether a node is present or not at each time step). The CNN outputs bar-level structure embeddings, which are concatenated and then compressed to obtain a structure embedding (Zs). Zc and Zs are concatenated and merged to obtain a graph latent code Zg . Parameters μ and σ are obtained by passing Zg through a linear layer. A latent vector Z is then sampled from $N(\mu, \sigma)$.

Both decoders largely mirror their respective encoders, using specular layers to decode Z into content and structure tensors. The structure decoder decodes Z to output a structure tensor S indicating node activations. The content decoder decodes Z while taking into account S , and outputs a content tensor of logits for the pitches and duration of each node.

Modifications from Polyphemus For the phrase generation model, we modified Polyphemus' CNN [4] to work for three tracks instead of four. The drum-related layers in the content encoder that accounted for percussion-pitched notes were removed since POP909 does not have a percussion track. For the song structure generation model, the CNN was further modified to work for two tracks. The number of layers in all models remained the same.

3.4 Training

Similar to Polyphemus, we used a β -VAE [12] loss function, where the Lagrangian multiplier (β) is appended to the KL-term in the loss function to adjust the

trade-off between reconstruction accuracy and latent bottleneck capacity. We trained the phrase generation model with a batch size of 32. β started at 0 for 5,000 steps of weight updates, then increased by 0.001 every 2,000 steps. The structure generation model had a batch size of 8. β started at 0 for 2,000 steps, then increased by 0.001 every 800 steps. Both models follow the hyper-parameter settings in Polyphemus: 8 layers in the encoder and decoder GCN, with a latent dimension of 512. Adam optimizer was used with an initial learning rate of 1e-4, which was decayed exponentially after 8000 gradient updates with a decay factor of 1- 5e-6. Both models were trained for 150 epochs.

4 Evaluation

We evaluated our phrase generation model and song structure generation model separately. By sampling from the latent space to generate new phrases and song structures, we compare the distribution with that of the ground truths of human-composed music¹.

4.1 Phrase Generation Model

We randomly generated 100 latent codes, and used the model decoder to generate 4-bar phrases from the latent codes. We measured the quality of the generated phrases by evaluating their (i) similarity to the training distribution, and (ii) ability to reproduce structural nuances.

Phrase-level distribution: The following are metrics for each phrase:

1. Empty Bar Rate (P_{EB}): Defined as the proportion of empty bars to the total number of bars, calculated as $P_{EB} = \frac{N_{\text{empty bars}}}{N_{\text{total bars}}}$, where $N_{\text{empty bars}}$ is the number of empty bars and $N_{\text{total bars}}$ is the total number of bars in the piece.
2. Used Pitch Class (N_{UPC}): The number of different pitch classes used per bar, where each count reflects the unique pitch classes in a given bar.

We compare the metrics for 100 generated phrases (GraphMuGen) and the pre-processed phrases (POP909) in Table 1. We observe that our model generates fewer pitch classes and more empty bars compared to POP909 phrases. For a benchmark, we randomly generated 100 tracks using Polyphemus (Polyph-LMD-4), and compared its metrics against LMD-4 (Table 2). We observe that the generated tracks for Drums and Bass have empty bars and pitch classes similar to LMD-4. However, for the Strings and Guitar tracks, the P_{EB} is significantly higher in the generated tracks as compared to the original data. This is similar to what we observed for GraphMuGen. Furthermore, the N_{UPC} for Strings is also higher in LMD-4 than from the generated tracks. This shows that the model has varying ability to generate pitch classes and activations for different types of tracks. The model performs well for tracks with more consistent rhythm like Drums and Bass, but less so for Strings, Guitar, and Piano parts.

¹ Visualization of metrics and audio samples: <https://graphmugen.notion.site/>

Table 1. Distribution metrics for POP909 (Ground Truth) and GraphMuGen output. M: Melody; B: Bridge; P: Piano

	Empty Bar (EB)			Used Pitch Class (UPC)		
	M	B	P	M	B	P
POP909	1.01	4.69	0.39	3.33	2.62	4.68
GraphMuGen	9.85	21.8	1.25	2.03	1.39	3.33

Table 2. Metrics for Polyphemus. D: Drums; B: Bass; S: Strings; G: Guitar

	Empty Bar (EB)				Used Pitch Class (UPC)		
	D	B	S	G	B	S	G
LMD (4-bar)	0.79	0.64	1.1	1.5	2.27	2.91	1.91
Polyph-LMD4	0.25	0.5	6.3	5.7	2.14	1.24	1.70

Phrase-level music theory attributes: To address the challenges highlighted by Dai [6], we adopted the metrics in their analysis to evaluate the model’s ability to reproduce phrase-level harmonic trends. We define them as follows:

1. Chord Frequency Probability (P_{CF}): Defined for each chord i as

$$P_{CF,i} = \frac{N_{\text{chord},i}}{N_{\text{chords, bar}}}, \quad (1)$$

where $N_{\text{chord},i}$ is the count of the i -th chord and $N_{\text{chords, bar}}$ is the total number of chords per bar.

2. Melody Pitch Class Frequency Probability (P_{PCF}): Calculated for each pitch class j as

$$P_{PCF,j} = \frac{N_{\text{pitch class},j}}{N_{\text{pitches, bar}}}, \quad (2)$$

where $N_{\text{pitch class},j}$ is the count of the j -th pitch class and $N_{\text{pitches, bar}}$ is the total number of pitches per bar.

3. Melody Pitch Entropy (H_{MPE}): The Shannon entropy for pitches per bar is computed as

$$H_{MPE} = - \sum_{k=1}^K p_{\text{pitch},k} \log_2(p_{\text{pitch},k}), \quad (3)$$

where $p_{\text{pitch},k}$ is the probability of the k -th pitch, and K is the total number of unique pitches.

The Chord and Pitch classes are based on the inferred Key of the phrase, using the `music21` library [5]. In Table 3, we observe that the chord frequency

probabilities for GraphMuGen remains mostly similar across all 4 bars. Chords V and I had significantly higher probabilities than other chords, with Chord V having the highest probability in Bar 1, but levelled out with Chord I in bar 4. Comparatively, in POP909, Chord I is most the frequent chord throughout the phrase. While there are some differences from the chord progressions of POP909, the generated phrases showed similar chord distributions, where chords I and V were most commonly used, and chords VII and IV were more sparsely used.

Table 3. Chord and melody frequency probabilities (%) by phrase position on POP909 and 100 GraphMuGen generated phrases

Bar	POP909 (Chord)							GraphMuGen (Chord)							POP909 (Melody)							GraphMuGen (Melody)						
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	32	13	11	9	24	9	2	23	13	17	8	33	4	2	16	16	21	3	18	18	7	11	20	20	7	18	16	8
2	31	11	14	7	21	12	2	29	15	14	8	32	3	1	15	17	19	3	18	19	7	19	23	10	6	17	16	8
3	28	12	15	9	18	16	2	26	14	17	7	28	6	2	17	17	18	3	18	19	7	12	20	15	4	18	22	9
4	27	14	13	11	21	13	2	28	10	18	9	26	9	1	17	19	18	4	17	19	7	21	15	19	5	18	16	7

Comparing melody pitch classes within a phrase, the generated phrases had more variance in pitch class probabilities (Table 3), while POP909 phrases showed consistent pitch class probabilities. The generated phrases still captured some of the distributions, where pitch classes 4 and 7 were rarely used. Despite the varying pitch class distribution in our generated phrases, the entropy of melody pitches was lower than that of POP909. This might be due to our model generating more empty bars than seen in POP909, resulting in sparser pitches. Despite this, the generated phrases captured the structural trend in melody pitch entropies, where the start of phrases have a lower entropy than the rest of the phrases.

4.2 Song Structure Generation Model

Our model is able to reconstruct the type, length and Melody/Non-Melody activations, with 88.7%, 83.4%, and 91.2% accuracies respectively on the Test set. To evaluate its ability to generate new song structures, we randomly generated 100 latent codes, and used the model decoder to generate song structures from them. We measured the quality of the generated song structures by comparing its similarity to the training distribution. We adopted the metrics from Dai et al. [7] in their analysis of structure in POP909. We define them as follows:

1. Number of Phrases per Song (N_{phrases}):

$$N_{\text{phrases}} = \text{total phrases in song} \tag{4}$$

2. Number of Unique Phrases per Song (U_{phrases}):

$$U_{\text{phrases}} = \text{unique phrases in song} \tag{5}$$

3. Frequency Probability of Phrase Length ($P_{\text{length}}(l)$):

$$P_{\text{length}}(l) = \frac{\text{count of phrases of length } l}{\text{total phrases}}. \quad (6)$$

Table 4. Metrics for phrase structure distribution, comparing ground truth POP909 and generated outputs from GraphMuGen.

	Num Phrases		Num Unique Phrases		Phrase Length	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std	Mean	Std
POP909	10.67	1.36	6.49	1.28	6.52	2.35
GraphMuGen	11.11	1.48	5.67	1.06	6.45	3.21

The metrics for POP909 were calculated after truncating each song to have a maximum of 12 phrases. Table 4 shows that the generated song structures (GraphMuGen) have a similar distribution of number of phrases and number of unique phrases. They both have similar mean phrase length, but the generated song structures have more variance in phrase length. In POP909, most phrases were of either 8-bars (35%) or 4-bars (32%) long. Our model was able to capture a similar distribution (8-bar: 55%; 4-bar: 35%). The phrase types generated were also similarly distributed, with A and B phrases making up most of the phrases for both POP909 (A; 28% B: 28%) and generated phrase types (A; 27% B: 38%).

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Our research has shown that GraphMuGen accurately replicate the structural properties of training data, but improvements are needed in pitch accuracy and minimizing empty bars. Implementing a temperature threshold to prevent note activation for probabilities under 0.5 could enhance musicality.

During phrase model training, we noted a trade-off between the KL-Divergence (KLD) of the latent embedding and note losses, suggesting difficulties in achieving a well-generalized Normal latent embedding without compromising pitch and duration accuracy. Unlike GraphMuGen, which used only 5,000 examples, the Polyphemus model benefited from a larger dataset from the LakhMIDI database.

To advance our models, expanding the dataset by augmenting the POP909 phrases with pitch transposition or note variation and incorporating phrase types could significantly refine outputs. This includes differentiating between introductory and chorus phrases. Our song structure model currently captures basic phrase attributes like length and type but could improve by adding more complex phrase details such as pitch and structure. Enhancing this would allow the model to understand inter and intra-phrase relationships better, leading to more accurate content tensor generation. Furthermore, applying a heuristic in full song generation to select only tracks of the same key and removing non-melodic sections could enhance the consistency and quality of the music produced.

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